

NATURAL HONEY MARKET: EU28 AND BRICS COMPETITIVENESS EVIDENCES REGARDING MOUNTAIN NATURAL HONEY

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Abstract: The paper presents natural honey market conjuncture, accentuating the contribution of EU28 (European Union 28) and BRICS countries (Brazil, Russian Federation, India, China and South Africa) to the world market competitiveness. The presented countries hold more than a half of natural honey world production, being considered major players of the global market. Some of them are emergent countries and occupy an increasingly better place in the current structure of world trade. In the current pandemic crisis, the market of natural honey does not decline in trade value, quantity and some related indices, but increases. The analyzed indices regarding natural honey and countries competitiveness are Export Value, Revealed Comparative Advantage (RCA) for Agricultural Raw Materials (covering natural honey), Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI), Export Market Penetration (EMP). The paper presents evidences regarding mountain natural honey - manna honey, conifer honey and mountain multiflora honey, and how natural honey market is influenced by the indices presented above.

Keywords: natural honey, world honey conjuncture, mountain area, EU28 and BRICS competitiveness trade indices.

1. Introduction

World conjuncture of the natural honey commodity must be analyzed through relevant indices which influence this market on worldwide level. In this paper it has been chosen the indices share of Export in total world, Export Market Penetration (EMP), Revealed Comparative Advantage (RCA) for Agricultural Raw Materials (which cover the natural honey commodity) and Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI). Natural honey (NH) is a raw commodity which does not represent a high risking product for human health, being the main reason of trade linearity or rising in the current pandemic crisis. In general, world trade has decline in value and volume from the beginning of the COVID19 pandemic. Still, some of the products does not reduced in trade value and volume because are marketed in crude form and, consequently, does not affect the human health as much as processed food.

There are some other raw products which increase in trade value and volume, as oils, vegetables, fruits, and so on. But, the lowest degree of risk for human health is represented by natural honey, which does not expire and has a low degree of infection. In these respect, natural

honey could be considered the most important bioindicator of current emerging agricultural sector.

The paper presents the main natural honey world player, together with some relevant indices for the mentioned country associations (EU28 and BRICS), like Export Value, Revealed Comparative Advantage (RCA) for Agricultural Raw Materials group products, Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI), Export Market Penetration (EMP).

Export Value is the indicator that show the total value of a country export, and is reflecting the emergence of an industry into a country.

According to Word Bank (2020), Export Market Penetration (EMP) is calculated as the number of countries to which the reporter exports a particular product divided by the number of countries that report importing the product that year.

Revealed Comparative Advantage (RCA) or Balassa index compares a country's advantage for a product / raw material / economic good and is calculated as follows (World Bank, 2020; Covaci B., 2020):

$$RCA_{cp} = \frac{E_{cp} / \sum_{p \in P} E_{cp}}{\sum_{c' \in C} E_{c'p} / \sum_{c' \in C, p \in P} E_{c'p}}$$

where E represent Exports;

c, c' – Country index;

C – Set of countries;

p, p' –Commodity index and – Set of commodities.

The indicator of RCA compares for any industry its share in the total export of goods with the share held in the total import. The calculation of the indicator in the case of an industry takes into account, on the one hand on the one hand, the export of domestic production and, on the other hand, the competing imports domestic production (and not the import of intermediate goods for industrial production respectively). High values of the indicator reveal a comparative advantage for that industry. (Croitoru et al, 2001). For Agricultural Raw Materials the RCA is calculated taking into consideration products from agricultural field.

The indicator of the concentration of foreign trade (HHI) is obtained by determining the share of trade of a product or a group of products in the total trade. The relation used is:

$$I_x = \sum \left(\frac{x_i}{X} \right)^2$$

where: i is the number of products or group of products;

xi represents the exports of that product;

X represents the total export. (Covaci, 2016)

2. Methods and data

World bank data shows that EU28 and BRICS countries have an important share in total world trade. EMP for EU28 and BRICS countries present a table for 2018 as follow Brazil 12,62, Russian Federation 11,51, India 27,15, China 47,41, South Africa 12,13, Austria 18,64, Belgium 23,95, Bulgaria 10,09, Croatia 6,61, Cyprus 3,33, Czech Republic 17,00, Denmark 16,61, Estonia 6,52, Finland 11,36, France 32,49, Germany 39,82, Greece 9,54, Hungary 12,91, Ireland 9,27, Italy 35,61, Latvia 6,25, Lithuania 8,65, Luxembourg 5,90, Malta 2,99, Netherlands 27,07, Poland 20,73, Portugal 13,86, Romania 11,20, Slovakia 10,26, Slovenia 10,21, Spain 28,02, Sweden 17,29, United Kingdom 33,13.

RCA for 2017 present an important trend for EU28 and BRICS countries – showing the emergence of these country groups, as follow: Brazil 3,64, Russian Federation 1,92, India 0,86, China 11,82, South Africa 0,12, Austria 0,86, Belgium 0,7, Bulgaria 0,72, Croatia 3,5, Cyprus 0,94, Czech Republic 0,8, Denmark 2,08, Estonia 5,33, Finland 5,57, France 0,67, Germany 0,54

Greece 1,62, Hungary 0,38, Ireland 0,25, Italy 0,46, Latvia 8,53, Lithuania 1,81, Luxembourg 1,11, Malta 0,19, Netherlands 1,98, Poland 0,83, Portugal 2,05, Romania 0,96, Slovakia 0,64, Slovenia 1,23, Spain 0,77, Sweden 3,12, United Kingdom 0,43.

HHI index for 2018 present the world top for EU28 and BRICS countries as follow: Brazil 0,11, Russian Federation 0,04, India 0,05, China 0,06, South Africa 0,07, Austria 0,10, Belgium 0,07, Bulgaria 0,05, Croatia 0,06, Cyprus 0,04, Czech Republic 0,11, Denmark 0,06, Estonia 0,06, Finland 0,05, France 0,05, Germany 0,04, Greece 0,03, Hungary 0,09, Ireland 0,12, Italy 0,04, Latvia 0,05, Lithuania 0,04, Luxembourg 0,09, Malta 0,04, Netherlands 0,09, Poland 0,09, Portugal 0,08, Romania 0,08, Slovakia 0,07, Slovenia 0,07, Spain 0,06, Sweden 0,04, United Kingdom 0,05.

Regarding natural honey, these country groups have a share of 55,22% in total export. Brazil hold 3,41% in total natural honey market (world raking in natural honey top WR 9), Russian Federation 0,28% (WR 39), India 5,07% (WR 6), China 11,82% (WR 1), South Africa 0,12% (WR 49), Austria 0,86% (WR 25), Belgium 3,19% (WR 10), Bulgaria 2,07% (WR 16), Croatia 0,10% (WR 54), Cyprus insignificant (WR 86), Czech Republic 0,25 % (WR 40), Denmark 0,80% (WR 28), Estonia 0,02% (WR 69), Finland insignificant (WR 92), France 1,51% (WR 18), Germany 6,61% (WR 4), Greece 0,74% (29), Hungary 4,25% (WR 8), Ireland 0,33% (WR 37), Italy 1,37% (WR 20), Latvia 0,04 % (WR 63), Lithuania 0,25% (WR 40), Luxembourg insignificant (WR 84), Malta insignificant (WR 116), Netherlands 0,98% (WR 24), Poland 2,17% (WR 14), Portugal 0,63% (WR 31), Romania 2,20% (13), Slovakia 0,04% (WR 62), Slovenia 0,12% (WR 51), Spain 4,44% (WR 75), Sweden 0,07% (WR 55), United Kingdom 1,50% (WR 19).

Natural honey is different from region to region, from space to space. One of the complex natural honey is mountain honey. "Not all honey are made equal... There are 300 known types of honey, produced by over 20,000 honey bee species, that vary in flavor, color, and health effects. For this reason, honey type and composition vary with geography, and angiosperm and honey bee species distribution." (Otero & Bernolo, 2020)

Methods used in the paper are qualitative and quantitative. Qualitative, it has been studied many scientific and professional papers and

synthetized the important idea. Quantitative, the author took and processed data from World Bank, World Integrated Trade Solution and International Trade Centre websites.

3. Results

Analyzed trade indices show that EU28 and BRICS countries tend to become more powerful in world trade, especially in exports. (figure 1 and 2).

Fig. 1. EU28 trade market competitiveness – general, agricultural raw materials and natural honey indices

Fig. 2. BRICS trade market competitiveness – general, agricultural raw materials and natural honey indices

Emergent countries as China, India, Poland grew up in market penetration on worldwide trade, while others, Belgium, France, Germany, Italy, Netherlands, Spain and United Kingdom straighten their position in exports. Other countries as Denmark, Czech Republic and Hungary tend to occupy more in export market penetration in 2018.

In the last years, important countries from EU28 and BRICS, as Brazil, China, Croatia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Greece, Latvia, Portugal, and Sweden increased their comparative advantage for agricultural raw materials on worldwide. Others like Russian Federation, South Africa, Austria, Denmark, Greece, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Netherlands and Slovenia becomes emergent countries in RCA for agricultural raw materials. (figure 1 and 2)

As seen, Brazil, Austria, Czech Republic and Ireland present a good HHI, meaning that their products become more competitive in 2018. But other countries grew up in HHI world sharing, namely South Africa, Belgium, Hungary, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia. (figure 1 and 2)

Regarding natural honey, EU28 and BRICS countries are among the top 75% in the world ranking, the majority are in the first half of the rankings, and countries with relevant RCA between the first 6%. Some of the top leaders of the natural honey exports from EU28 and BRICS countries are Brazil, India, China, Belgium, Germany, Hungary, and Spain. Other countries become in the last years more competitive on the natural honey market, respectively France, Italy, Poland, Romania and United Kingdom. Romania is between the first 8% in the world ranking top. (figure 1 and 2)

Mountain natural honey is found in few forms such as manna honey, conifer honey and mountain multiflora honey. (Rey et. all, 2019). "Mountain honey is a hybrid grape tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) resulting from the cross of NC 4 grape × NC 6 grape... It has a compact indeterminate plant with short internodes conferred by the brachytic (br) gene and has dark red fruit with high total soluble solids." (Panthee & Randy, 2013)

In Romania mountain honey is the most appreciated type of honey, but not so consumed because is more expansive than others and insufficient promoted. In a major study realized in 2012, on 1449 persons, at the North-West region of Romania, the respondents answer that this type of honey is the most preferred, being impressed by it. As reminded, the problem with

this honey is the promotion, being insufficient advertised. (Pocol, 2012)

Mountain honey is preferred because has more benefits on health than others, like antiseptic, antimicrobial, anti-diabetic, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, wound healing, regulatory of blood pressure and cardiovascular function, anti-cancer. The most common known bioactive components of honey are probiotics, prebiotics, quercetin, hesperitin, luteolin, kaempferol, galangin, naringenin, isorhamnetin, bee defensin-1. (Otero & Bernolo, 2020)

Manna honey is the only assortment of honey that does not come totally from the nectar of flowers, its origin being credited from the sweet secretions of trees or the sweet excretion of aphids, small green insects. Thus, we can consider that manna honey can have either vegetable origin, result of plant secretion, or animal, taken from the excretion of aphids. Manna honey has the highest mineral content, being the highly prized, especially due to the fact that it can be consumed by people allergic to floral pollen. It is rightly considered a real mineral cocktail, the mineral content in manna honey being, for example, six times higher than in acacia honey. This variety of honey also contains antioxidants such as phenols or flavonoids. Also, there was a high content of bioactive components compared to other types of honey, the content of enzymes and antibiotics being much higher than honey from flower nectar. Manna honey has a special value for human consumption and due to the content of organic acids, bioflavonoids, vitamin C and B vitamins. Due to its high mineral content it is frequently recommended in the treatment of spasmophilia in adolescents, rickets in children and adolescents, in osteoporosis and joint disease in both adults and the elderly. (Terra Apis, 2020)

Conifer honey is a type of honey that bees produce by collecting sap from the leaves or branches of conifers such as fir, pine, spruce. Conifer honey is slightly more fragrant and can smell a slight smell of fir resin. Particularly important is the presence of over 30 species of endemic plants or declared monuments of nature, whose survival is not possible outside a network of protected areas. The coniferous forest is the largest terrestrial habitat in the world. Conifer honey could be one of the most quantitative and qualitative honey of the world. This type of honey is specific for antiseptic and respiratory disease. (Maxantifurti, 2020)

Mountain multiflora honey hints of fruits and berries in the distance and is made to over 850 meters above sea level. "Recent studies have shown how the biodiversity becomes richer in proportion to the mountain altitude, with an extraordinary increase in the number of flowers above 850 meters (with 80 different species in the spring and over 130 in the summer). Among the most common plants are many grasses, rock roses and mints, along with white clover, blackberry and other members of the rose family, poppies, sainfoin and bird's foot trefoil, while ivy and wild asparagus flower in the late summer." (Slow Food Foundation for Biodiversity, 2020)

Natural honey, if not properly stored, presents often problems regarding alteration. Spontaneous fermentation is the main form of honey alteration. The process is triggered by a wide range of yeasts, which can be associated with some bacteria capable of fermenting sugars. The main sources of pollution of bee products are the environment and the substances used by beekeepers for the treatment of bee diseases. The activity of bees is influenced by all elements of the environment (soil, vegetation, air and water). (Pohl, 2009). The yeasts influence is difficult to control perfectly, in consequence the honey production could be easily damaged if the entrepreneurs (producers and distributors) are not attentive to the entire biodiversity of the mentioned environment elements. In addition, S. Bogdanov (2006) points out that the danger of contamination of natural honey lies in a greater extent from beekeeping practices than from the environment. Beekeepers must take action to prevent contamination of bee products by opting for ecological alternatives in disease control, by using non-toxic natural substances instead of synthetic ones. The purity of bee products depends on the period of their collection, the type of plant composition and the location of the apiary location (Lebedev & Muratova, 2003). Lebedev & Muratova (2003) found that of all bee products, honey is a pure ecological product, propolis, pasture and pollen being more polluted with heavy metals (Eremia et al, 2016).

Conclusions

The paper shows that natural honey market is influenced by the world production and trade, and by related indices. In the article are presented the EU28 and BRICS because these country groups have more than a half of natural honey world market. The analyzed indices regarding

natural honey and countries competitiveness were Export Value, Revealed Comparative Advantage (RCA) for Agricultural Raw Materials (covering natural honey), Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI), Export Market Penetration (EMP).

Regarding world exports and export market penetration countries as China, India, Poland become emergently, while Belgium, France, Germany, Italy, Netherlands, Spain and United Kingdom straighten production and exports position.

RCA for agricultural raw materials presents an interesting worldwide picture, showing that Brazil, China, Croatia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Greece, Latvia, Portugal, and Sweden straightened their comparative advantage. Instead, countries like Russian Federation, South Africa, Austria, Denmark, Greece, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Netherlands and Slovenia become emergently in worldwide comparative advantage.

The last presented index, HHI, show that some of the countries, as Brazil, Austria, Czech Republic and Ireland, become more competitive on worldwide production and trade market, while South Africa, Belgium, Hungary, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, becomes emergently.

The paper presents evidences regarding mountain natural honey - manna honey, conifer honey and mountain multiflora honey, and show that these types of natural honey are excellent for health and nutrition. Consequently, mountain honey must be more promoted and people have to be educated in the spirit of consuming this type of honey. The countries with high RCA for agricultural raw materials, HHI and EMP could access easily the world honey market. But the country with significant mountain area could have an important trade advantage because of the mountain honey production.

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